

MANUFACTURING RELATED DEFECTS – WHERE AND WHY THEY OCCUR, AND DO THEY MATTER?

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FRPs are complex materials, assembled during manufacture. Components will include features/imperfections, and cost-effective design of structures and manufacturing processes will account for their presence.

Why do they occur? Can we detect them, and do they affect performance?

A **feature** is a measurable deviation from the ideal product form. Features occurring in critical regions, at sufficient strength, represent **defects**.

Effects of Defects has formed one of three streams, of a six year New Zealand funded research programme.

Projects have been organised around **three key questions**, as applied to processes and products defined by our industrial partners.

How do features develop?

- Influence of geometry
- Influence of layup
- Influence of environmental conditions

Can we detect features?

- NDT of textile structures
- Detection of bridging, wrinkling
- NDT of finished components

Are they defects? Do they matter?

- Impact of manufacturing related features

CONTENT

- Effects of Defects Programme
- Detection of Defects during Manufacture
- Determining Manufacturing Causes of Defects
- Concluding Remarks

Centre for
Advanced
Composite
Materials

THE UNIVERSITY OF
AUCKLAND
Te Whare Wānanga o Tamaki Makaurau
NEW ZEALAND

CONTENT

- **Effects of Defects Programme**
- **Detection of Defects during Manufacture**
 - **Non-Destructive Testing of Fibre Products**
 - **Defect Detection through Prepreg Processing**
- **Determining Manufacturing Causes of Defects**
- **Concluding Remarks**

NDT of Fibre Products

LESSONS FROM AN INDUSTRIAL EXPERIENCE AT BMW

1999

Assoc. Prof. Bickerton
• Composites researcher

Mar, 2012

Dr. Bickerton, MT-121
• CFRP Materials Team
• LT-1 Project Leader

Feb, 2015

Prof. Bickerton
• Composites researcher
• Director CACM (2016-)

NDT of Fibre Products

VALUE OF NON-DESTRUCTIVE MATERIAL TESTING

Within the materials team, we established a variety of fibre product material measurements for quality control and problem solving...

... for fibre tow, textile, stacks, and preforms.

While we focussed on fast measurements, the majority of techniques **destroyed the product/sample**, and the **cost of testing was high**.

Key Lesson: Methods should be **non-destructive** to minimise cost and provide deeper process insight, and **very fast and easy to interpret**.

NDT of Fibre Products

DEVELOPMENT OF AN ADVANCED PROTOTYPE

Initial air permeability trials at BMW led to a funded UoA Project

- Prototyping and developing an industrial test method
- Developing and delivering an advanced prototype

Key

- | | |
|--------------------------|--------------------------------|
| ① Pressure Sensor (Head) | ④ Pressure Sensor (Vessel) |
| ② Top Receiver / Plate | ⑤ Pressure Switch |
| ③ Solenoid Valve | ⑥ Automatic Pressure Regulator |

NDT of Fibre Products

NON-DESTRUCTIVE INJECTABILITY/COMPRESSIBILITY

- No requirement to cut a sample
- Two interchangeable heads provide in-plane and through-thickness measurement
- Based on transient air pressure pulse, and a single pressure transducer
- **Injectability** is taken to be the exponential decay coefficient, **b**

The injectability/compressibility prototype has been applied to detect defects in 2D and 3D preforms; including **folds**, **wrinkles**, and **gaps** in layers.

This simple measurement concept enables **fully automated** assessment of stacks and preforms.

- **Determination** of lower and upper **controls limits** for process stabilisation.
- Industry 4.0 / Smart Production ready

 Fold – Decreases the local injectability

NDT of Fibre Products

APPLICATION FOR DETECT DETECTION

- First 2D preform tests at BMW, undertaken late 2016
- Defects detected/grouped, by combined compression and injectability measures
- Applied to 112 3D production preforms, in study at a BMW production line in 2017

Gaps	1x Fold	2x Fold	3x Fold
▲ 5 mm	▲ 5 mm	▲ 5 mm	▲ 5 mm
◆ 10 mm		◆ 10 mm	◆ 10 mm
● 15 mm	● 15 mm		● 15 mm
■ 20 mm	■ 20 mm	■ 20 mm	■ 20 mm

NDT of Fibre Products

TOWARDS IN-TOOL, IN-LINE MEASUREMENTS

Two configurations studied, for application in cutting or preforming tools:

Closed mould tool:

Measurement cells

Open mould tool:

Measurement cells

A one inlet, two outlet linear flow measurement cell was developed, based on air pressures:

- No need for historical data, or accurate sample thickness control, to detect defects
- Dedicated clamping zones do not improve feature detection
- Relative pressure difference between ports is influenced by the boundaries
 - Open mould design preferred

$$P_{rel} = \sqrt{\left(0.5 - \frac{P_{R/L}}{P_R + P_L}\right)^2}$$

(a) Reference – Pressure distribution

(b) Feature 1, guided – two-layer fold

(c) Feature 4, guided – two-layer fold

NDT of Fibre Products

MEASUREMENT CELL VALIDATION

Proof of concept through experimental validation

- Artificial feature implementation within real preforms
- Seven feature configuration with different severity were tested (guided, non-guided)

Feature	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Non-Guided							

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Defect Detection through Prepreg Processing

SUMMARY OF APPLIED METHODS

Several methods have been employed to observe quality through **all three phases** of processing.

- **Laser gauges**, to monitor laminate thickness through layer by layer application
- **Snap curing** of debulked layups, to examine laminate quality before and after consolidation
- **Tekscan measurements**, to correlate pressure distribution in corners defect generation

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 - Environmental and Geometrical Effects on Autoclave Processing of Prepregs
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Environmental Influences on Resin Infusion

OBJECTIVE STUDY OF RESIN INFUSION TECHNIQUES

A comparative study was completed on six infusion techniques, considering process robustness, and resulting laminate composition.

Filing

Post-filing

Environmental Influences on Resin Infusion

OBJECTIVE STUDY OF RESIN INFUSION TECHNIQUES

Fibre Volume Fraction

Short Beam Strength

CLC Compression Strength

Environmental Influences on Resin Infusion

THE INFLUENCE OF DISSOLVED GASES IN LIQUID EPOXY

Utilising oxygen content as a quantitative measure of dissolved gases in a liquid epoxy resin, the following studies were completed:

- Absorption and desorption rates, and effectiveness of degassing
- Correlation of gas saturation levels to final laminate void content
- Influence of dissolved oxygen on laminate mechanical properties

Oxygen Absorption, varying Resin Depth

Oxygen Desorption during Degassing, and Influence of Applied Vacuum Pressure

Environmental Influences on Resin Infusion

THE INFLUENCE OF DISSOLVED GASES IN LIQUID EPOXY

Oxygen saturation is a function of resin pressure, and over-saturation with oxygen has been strongly correlated to void generation in post-filling.

This diagram summarises the relationship between applied pressure in post-filling, saturation content of oxygen, and resulting voids.

Laminate produced with over-saturated resin:

Laminate produced with under-saturated resin:

Laminate CLC Compression Strength

Note: Large inter-tow voids did not reduce strength.

Environmental Influences on Resin Infusion

THE INFLUENCE OF ABSORBED MOISTURE

The influence of environmental humidity has been considered in the following studies. Materials were conditioned at various humidities, and infusion completed within an environmental chamber.

- Absorption and desorption into fibre, resin, and consumables
- Detailed studies of absorption/desorption to/from liquid epoxy resin
- Influence of absorbed moisture on mechanical properties

**Fibre and Consumables,
Total Moisture Absorption**

Liquid Epoxy Moisture Absorption/Desorption

**- Influence of
Atmospheric Humidity**

**- Influence of Vacuum
Pressure during Drying**

Environmental Influences on Resin Infusion

THE INFLUENCE OF ABSORBED MOISTURE

Laminate produced in a 30% relative humidity environment:

Laminate produced in a 90% relative humidity environment:

Laminate CLC
Compression Strength

Resin Tensile Modulus

Resin Tensile Strength

Resin Strain to Failure

Resin Stress-Strain Curves

Environmental Influences on Resin Infusion

COMPARING ROBUST INFUSION TO AUTOCLAVE PREPREG

A hybrid CAPRI-VAP infusion method has been applied, including careful control of environmental issues, to compare properties of laminates prepared using infusion and prepreg processing.

- Chomarat 150gsm [0/+30/-30], [0/+45/-45] textiles
- T700S Fibres
- Half of material prepregged by GMS composites with EP-280

0/45/-45 Infusion

0/45/-45 Prepreg

Fibre Volume Fraction

Void Content

Compression Strength

Interlaminar Shear Strength

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Environmental and Geometric Influences, Prepreg ASSESSMENT OF LAYUP, DEBULKING AND AUTOCLAVE CONSOLIDATION

Wrinkling

l...length
A...amplitude

Voids / Porosity

Environmental and Geometric Influences, Prepreg

DEFECTS IN CORNERS OF AN AFT MAST SECTION

40% rel. humidity samples

Debulking

Curing

90% rel. humidity samples

Debulking

Curing

Environmental and Geometric Influences, Prepreg

DEFECTS IN CORNERS OF AN AFT MAST SECTION, WITH PATCHES

40% rel. humidity samples

Macro

Microscopy

90% rel. humidity samples

Microscopy

Macro

Environmental and Geometric Influences, Prepreg

QUANTIFYING MOISTURE ABSORPTION/DESORPTION IN LAYUP/DEBULKING

Moisture Absorption at 40% RH

Moisture Absorption at 90% RH

Effectiveness of Drying during Debulking

Rel. Humidity	Time until fully saturated (1 Layer)	Max. rel. weight gain	Diffusion Coefficient (m ² /s)
40%	25 hours	0.12 %	1.29E-12
90%	25 hours	0.25 %	1.21E-12

Environmental and Geometric Influences, Prepreg

INVESTIGATING EFFECTIVE PRESSURE APPLIED IN CORNERS

Sample Size 90 x 150mm

- Calibration on flat surface
- Calibration Force: 320N
- Vacuum Pressure: 20mbar
- Corner Radius: 14mm

Sample after effective
layup/debulking

Sample including bridging after
layup/debulking

Environmental and Geometric Influences, Prepreg

INFLUENCE OF ABSORBED MOISTURE ON PRESSURE APPLIED IN CORNERS

0° Fibre Direction Laminates

0°/90° Fibre Direction Laminates

Laminate consolidation simulation via ABAQUS is under development, to predict formation of wrinkle defects in corners. A broad prepreg material characterisation programme is underway, including the influence of absorbed moisture (40%, 60%, 90% rel. H).

Prepreg Material Characterisation

- Moisture Diffusion Coefficient
- Moisture Absorption/Desorption
- Prepreg Tack
- Compaction Behaviour
- Interply Friction
- Bending Stiffness

Process Simulation

- Compaction Behaviour
 - Compaction Pressure Distribution in Corners
- ↓
- **Defect Prediction Simulation**

Fully fixed plate

Prepreg compaction
behaviour simulation

Wrinkling model applying
compression load by a bridged bag.

Compaction Response of Cross Plied Samples

Elevated Temperature Compaction

Peel/Tack Measurement

Comparison of Peel Force with Fibre Direction

Features are developed through the steps of a FRP processing chain, and are considered **defects** when generated in **critical regions of a part**, and **above critical severity**.

Non-destructive testing along the process chain provides several benefits:

- Ability to reject defective materials/products early in the process chain.
- Ability to correlate the measurement to process performance in later steps in the process chain.
- Application to Quality Control, materials and process qualification, as well as problem solving.

Improved understanding is required on the sources, and the influence of features on part performance, to inform design and Quality Control.

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